

AIJACLA

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs

Vol. 1

January, 2021

About the Journal

An International,
Double-blind,
Peer-reviewed and
Annually published
Journal.

Contact Details

Email:

aequitasvictoria@gmail.com

Helpline Number:

8473808112

Office Address:

H/o Shri Sarthak Aryan,
C/o Shri Subodh Kumar,
Old Madhya Bihar Gramin
Bank Building,
Sakurabad
P.O.: Sakurabad,
Dist: Jehanabad,
PIN: 804425 (Bihar).

Published By

**Aequitas Victoria
Foundation**

www.aequivic.in

AEQUITAS VICTORIA FOUNDATION PRESENTS
ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ANALYSIS OF CONTEMPORARY
LEGAL AFFAIRS

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Annual International Journal on Analysis of Contemporary Legal Affairs (AIJACLA) is an annual international double-blind peer-reviewed journal in the field of law. The journal deals with contemporary affairs primarily within the discipline of law but also encourages interdisciplinary research works from any discipline provided the relation of the subject-matter with the legal institutions, legal instruments, or any other legal matters shall be established and highlighted to meet the eligibility criteria of the journal.

Broadly the Journal welcomes research works from each branch of law like: Human Rights, Humanitarian Rights, IPR, Environmental Law, Public and Private International Law, Air and Space Law, Drone Law, Martial Law, Sports Law, Fashion Law, etc. It even encourages contributions from panel discussion or conference reports based on the topics of recent developments in the field of law. Further, case commentaries, law book reviews, legislative and policy analysis are also welcomed. The journal will also publish contributions that are not expressly from the discipline of law but establishes a relation with any of the legal matters and gives it an interdisciplinary character.

However, comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws.

SCOPE

The scope of this journal extends to the entire world transcending all national boundaries of the States. It is an international journal aimed at establishing a global network of research and analysis in the field of law. The medium of publication will be primarily **American English** subject to the majority opinion of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, and the Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee.

The Journal is expected to be a globally open accessed journal subject to the technical limitations and international or regional laws in force or existence anywhere either internationally or nationally.

The journal intends to cover all fields of law including-

1. International Conventions passed by International or Global Bodies;
2. Regional Conventions, Rules, Policies, etc. passed by Regional Organizations that are recognized globally;
3. Rules, Policies, By-laws, etc. passed by any Inter-state bodies provided such matters influence the relationship between two or more countries that are recognized as sovereign under the international rules;
4. Any other Conventions, Laws, Rules, etc. that are not directly recognized by any international or global bodies or agencies but are going to influence or has an impact on the diplomatic relationships between two or more countries;
5. Cases decided by International Adjudicating Authorities;
6. Any Laws, By-laws, Enactments, Policies, etc. passed by a proper legislative authority, competent courts, authorities with proper legal recognitions in any sovereign country;
7. Conference, Seminar, Colloquium, etc. reports that are based on topics of law;
8. Lectures from eminent professionals in the field of law, or lectures on legal topics from eminent personalities;
9. Researches made on Theories relevant to the field of Law;
10. Any researchable topic from any discipline provided the subject-matter of such research shall properly establish the nexus with the legal institutions, instruments, or any other subject-matter of law; and
11. Results of researches carried out independently either as an individual, group, or as an organization in the field of law.

However, the journal shall not publish any material related to the following either in whole or in part subject to the approval of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team including the Managing Committee-

1. Comments regarding decisions pending before any Court of Law or any other subject matter across the globe which if published might lead to Contempt of Court, if interpreted from the perspective of Indian Jurisprudence, will not be published even if the matter does not violate any of the Indian Laws or does not amount to any offense in any other laws;
2. Political opinions even if based on legal topics that are suspected of influencing voting behavior of the citizens of any sovereign country against the provisions of an established legislations either international, regional, or local, or is expected to incite rebellion or conflict against any popularly established government; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee;
3. Any discriminatory opinions regarding racial, gender, or any other class of people, or comments in favor of any particular group, institution, organization, party, community, etc.; provided such materials may be published considering the authenticity of the sources, the justification of the author(s), the need and demand of the time or situation and above all the decision of the Board of Editors, Expert Committee, Board of Advisors in conformity with the Core Team along with the Managing Committee; or
4. Any other immoral, offensive, comments, or comments against any established custom or culture.

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide a platform for Indian Legal Professionals including Judges, Academicians, Advocates, and Students for showcasing their research skills;
2. To build an endeavor of research and analytical altitude amongst the young legal professionals under the experience and guidance of the senior legal experts;
3. To highlight the possible developments needed in the area of law through research and analytical spirits;
4. To encourage the habit of critical analysis and argumentative behavior amongst the law students; and
5. To help in policy formulation and legal drafting in India by expressing suggestions brought forward through research skills.

BOARD OF EDITORS

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. (Dr) Chintamani Rout

HOD. Department of Law
North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong

Senior Editor

Prof. (Dr) Yugal Kishore

Professor of Law, ICFAI Law School,
ICFAI University Dehradun, Former
Professor, Registrar, Vice-Chancellor
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Senior Editor

Dr. Heru Susetyo

Assistant professor, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Chairman of the Center for Islam and
Islamic Law, Faculty of Law,
Universitas Indonesia, Jakarta,
Indonesia.

Senior Editor

Mrs. Ronaldah Lerato Karabo Ozah

Director- Litigation, Research and
Advocacy and Lecturer, Centre for
Child Law, University of Pretoria, South
Africa.

Senior Editor

Dr Dhruvajyoti Das

Associate Professor, Department of
English, Cotton University

Senior Editor

Dr. Sachin Ghimire

Medical Anthropologist and Filmmaker
Assistant professor, Department of
Public health, Manamohan Memorial
Institute of Health Sciences(MMIHS),
Kathmandu, Nepal.

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Senior Editor

Dr. Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor, University Law
College Gauhati University

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Dharmashastra
National Law University, Jodhpur

Associate Editors

Ms. Moushita Dutta

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Mrs. Mageswary Siva Subramaniam

Lecturer with Faculty of Law,
Multimedia University (Malacca
Campus), Malacca, Malaysia.
Visiting lecturer, Lingnan University,
Hong Kong

Associate Editors

Mr. Animesh Jha

Assistant Professor, Family Law,
Dharmashastra National Law University
(DNLU), Jabalpur.

Mrs. Rima Borthakur

Former Senior Manager, Document
Review department in Thomson Reuters
(Pangea3), New York City.

Associate Editors

Mr. Prithvi Raaj Choudhury

LLM, McGill University, Montreal,
Canada.

Associate Editors

Mr. Amey Pandey

Co-Founder CLAT Junction, Working
with Safe in India Foundation

EXPERT COMMITTEE

**Prof (Dr) Bhaskar Kumar
Chakravarty**

Visiting Professor of Law Royal Global
University, Former Professor Dean and
Head Department of Law, Gauhati
University, Founder Head of
Department of Law, Tezpur University

Dr Gautami Dutta

Principal R.K.B. Law College

Dr Anup Kumar Ray

Principal, Goalpara Law College

Prof (Dr) Atul Chandra Talukdar

Dean School of Social Science &
Humanities, University of Science &
Technology Meghalaya

Dr Ajay Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Dr Md. Sultan Haidar Alam

Principal NERIM Law College

Dr Kasturi Gakul

Assistant Professor of Law
National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Dr Bimal Kumar Baishya

Associate Professor (Rtd.), University
Law College Gauhati University

Dr Sujata Bhattacharyya

Principal Nowgong Law College

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria

Editor Nyaijyoti, All Assam Lawyers
Association

REVIEW COMMITTEE

Mrs. Dimpy Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashmi Gogoi

Research Scholar Gauhati University
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Mrs. Karishma Saikia

Assistant Professor, Nowgong Law
College

Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Darshana Deepak Das

MA in English Litt (Specialization in
Indian Literature), PGT in Potential and
Concept Academy, Working as an SME
in AMF Edu Solutions
Designation: Member Content

Suyash Pranay Tripathi

PGDCPLP, National Law School of
India University Bangalore, LLM
National Law University, Odisha
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Anya Behera

LLM from National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB from
KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Rashi Gupta

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB
Vivekananda Institute of Professional
Studies, New Delhi
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Alekh

LLM, National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Srishti

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Aadya Ambastha
Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Ishan Mishra

Student
ICFAI Law College, Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Assessment Committee

Girisha Sinha

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB KIT
Law School Bhubaneswar
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Prachi Prem

Student at Chanakya National Law
University, Bihar
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Monalisa Choudhury

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Ishan Mishra
Student at ICFAI University Dehradun
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Pranay Rathore

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Riya Kumari

Student at University Law College,
Hazaribagh
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Shreya Gupta

Student at JIMS Engineering
Management Technical Campus, Noida
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

Prachi Nayan

LLM National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam, LLB, ICFAI
Law School, Dehradun
Designation: Member Content
Assessment Committee

Saloni Sharma

Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Bomkesh Mandal

Student at National Law University,
Assam
Riya Sharma
Student at Fairfield Institute of
Management and Technology, New
Delhi
Designation: Format Assessment
Committee

Basuri Poddar

Student at National Law University and
Judicial Academy Assam
Designation: Member Plagiarism and
Ethics Review Committee

CORE TEAM (MANAGING COMMITTEE)

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary

Ms Vidisha Dixit

Hon'ble Member

Mrs Pranati Boruah

Hon'ble President

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Hon'ble Member (Founder)

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Hon'ble Member

Mr Sarthak Aryan

Hon'ble Member (Co-Founder)

ADMINISTRATIVE SECTION

Executive Committee

Chief Executive Officer

Ms Kashmiri Khanam

Assistant Professor, Dhubri Law
College, Research Scholar, Central
University of Haryana

Executive Officer

Ms Saloni Sharma

Fairfield Institute of Management and
Technology, New Delhi
Executive Officer

Ms Darshee Madhukallya

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Content Designer

Ms Abhishree Kashay

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Basnuri Poddar

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Gautami Chakravarty

KIT School of Law Bhubaneswar

Executive Officer

Ms Riya Kumari

University Law College, Hazaribagh

Content designer

Bonaini Deori

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Ms Nijhum Roy

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Event Manager

Ms Puja Bardhan

West Guwahati Commerce College

Event Manager

Ms Nargis Choudhury

Former Lecturer, School of Law and
Judicial Sciences, Apex Professional
University, Arunachal Pradesh

Executive Officer

Mr Chetan Anand Mahapatra

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Executive Officer

Ms Shreya Gupta

JIS Engineering Management Technical
Campus, Noida

Content Designer

Ms Dikshita Nanda Nath

Advocate, Gauhati High Court

Content Designer

Mr Arunabh Chakravarty

Department of English, Gauhati
University

Event Manager

Mr Debanjan Das

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam

Disciplinary Committee

**Advocate Rajendra Singh
Suryavanshi**

Advocate, Supreme Court of India

Chairman

Mr Manik Chandra Boruah

Rtd. Police Officer, Assam Police
Hon'ble Member Managing Committee,
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mrs Nidhi Tiwari

Hon'ble Secretary, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Mr Jayanta Boruah

Former Assistant Professor NERIM
Law College, Advocate Gauhati High
Court and Research Scholar North-
Eastern Hill University, Hon'ble
Member The Managing Committee
Aequitas Victoria Foundation

Mr Subodh Kumar

Hon'ble Treasurer, The Managing
Committee, Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Grievance Redressal Committee

Advocate Dr Lalan Prasad Thakuria
Member, All Assam Lawyers
Association

Chairman

Dr Matiur Rahman

Assistant Professor
University Law College Gauhati
University

Dr Ajoy Kumar Das

Principal, Jorhat Law College

Mrs Roseleen Deori

Assistant Professor
Nowgaong Law College

VOLUME 1
(Editorial Special Issue)
2020

Ms Vidisha Dixit
Hon'ble Member The Managing
Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

Media Cell

Mrs Kangkana Goswami
Assistant Editor NE News

Mr Sandeep Deo
Founder, India Speaks Daily
Mrs Prity Deka
Assistant Manager, Axis Bank

Mr Bishaldeep Kakoti
Founder, The Youths Mind

IT Section

Ishita Gupta

United College of Engineering and
Research, Prayagraj

Mr Sarthak Aryan

National Law University and Judicial
Academy Assam, Hon'ble Member The
Managing Committee Aequitas Victoria
Foundation

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Sl No.	Title of Papers and Names and Designations of Authors	Page No.
SECTION A: RESEARCH PAPERS		
1	Affirmative Principle: Making, Breaking and Shaking (MBS) Approach of Judiciary <i>-Dr Rangswami D, Assistant Professor of Law, Karnataka State Law University, Hubballi, Karnataka</i>	1 - 17
2	Clinical and Continuing Legal Education- Interface for Confidence Building Between Law Students and Legal Professionals in Contemporary India <i>- Dr. Md. Sultan Haidar Alam, Principal, NERIM Law College</i>	18 - 29
3	A Critical Appraisal of the Legal Service Authorities Act with Special Reference to Lok Adalat <i>- Dr. Dhiraj Bhusan Sarmah, Former Faculty of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University & Dr. Plabita Saikia, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	30 - 49
4	Establishment of DNA Data Bank in India: A Legal Analysis <i>- Dr. Ranjit Sil, Assistant Professor, Department Of Law, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong</i>	50 - 64
5	Ecocentric Approaches of the Restorative Justice Theory Vis-à-vis the Legal Issues of Civil and Criminal Liability of the Baghjan Blowout Case in Assam <i>- Dr. Matiur Rahman, Assistant Professor of Law, University Law College, Gauhati University</i>	65 - 76
6	A Comparative Study on Secondary Patenting on Pharmaceutical: Striking A Balance Between Competition Law and IPR <i>- Dr. Kakumani Katakya, Faculty of Law Gauhati University</i>	77 - 90
7	Community and Environmental Protection- - In Search of the Lost Spring of Happiness of the North-Eastern Region <i>- Dr. Sujata Bhattacharyya, Principal, Nowgong Law College</i>	91 - 106
8	National Emergency: A Comparative Analysis of Emergency Laws in India USA and Germany <i>- Abhishek Kumar Khaund, Advocate. Gauhati High Court</i>	107 - 124
9	Legal Frameworks Relating to Use of Pesticides on Horticultural Activities Vis-à-vis Climate Change <i>- Bonani Deori, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Mritunjoy Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	125 -145
20	The Arms Act, 1959: A Legal Analysis and Comparative Study with USA <i>- Bikash Sen Deka, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	146 -168
11	Comparative Study on Intergovernmental Tax Immunities under the Federal Constitutions of Australia, Canada, India and USA <i>- Bandita Das, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	169 - 177
12	Unlawful Activities and Prevention Act: Balancing National Security with Citizen's Rights <i>- Girisha Sinha, Research Assistant under Advocate Ritesh Kumar Patna High Court</i>	178 - 191
13	An Analysis of the Legal Framework of the Co-operative Banks in India	192 - 215

	- Bidikha Gogoi, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
14	Parole- The Reformative Instrument of Punishment in Prisonization	216 -228
	- Nayana Medhi, Former Faculty of Law, Indraprastha University	
15	Assam Police and Its Organizational Structure	229 - 271
	- Dr. Anup Kr. Ray, Principal, Goalpara Law College	
SECTION B: ARTICLES		
16	Anti-Defection Law: A Conflict Between the Right to Dissent and the Integrity of the Political Party	273 - 281
	- Apurva Mehta, B.A. LL.B. (Criminal Law Hons.), 5th Year, National University of Study and Research in Law, Ranchi	
17	Contempt of Court: An Urgent Requisite to Re-Explore	282 - 287
	- Paras Gupta, B.A.LL.B.(Hons.), Institute of Law, Kurukshetra University	
18	Lack of Uniform Code of Conduct to Address the Judges in India	288 - 294
	- Saloni Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology & Riya Sharma, 3rd Year B.B.A.LL.B, Fairfield Institute of Management and Technology	
19	Rejuvenating the Right to Equality and Life under the Paradigm of Transformative Constitution	295 - 301
	- Dr. Daisy Changmai, Faculty of Law, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam, Former Principal of Dibrugarh Hanumanbux Surojmal Kanoi Law College	
20	Genital Mutilation- An Appeal for Legislative Response in India to Outlaw the Menace	302 - 311
	- Dr. Karavi Barman, Assistant Professor, N.E.F Law College, Guwahati	
21	Surrogacy in India: A Legal Perspective	312 - 319
	- Dr. Shrutimala Goswami, Assistant Professor, NERIM Law College & Arunav Barua., Research Scholar, Assam Don Bosco University	
22	Merger and Amalgamation of Companies in India: AN Analysis of Its Impact on Various Stakeholders	320 - 330
	- Purbaja Sarmah, Advocate, Gauhati High Court	
23	Human Rights Crisis amongst IDPs in Assam: Issues and Challenges	331 - 337
	- Dr. Gautami Dutta, Principal, Dr. R.K.B. Law College, Dibrugarh	
24	Protective Discrimination under the Constitution of India	338 -345
	- Pallabi Nath, LL.M 1 st Semester, Tezpur University	
25	Mob Lynching as a New Offence Emerging in India: A Study with a Special Reference to Assam	346 - 355
	- Nargis Choudhury, Former Faculty of Legal Studies, School of Law and Juridical Sciences Apex Professional University, Pasighat, Arunachal Pradesh	
26	The Doctrine of Pious Obligation and Its Relevance under the Hindu Law in the Present Time	356 - 363
	-Titikhya Barkataki, LL.M, 1st Semester, Gauhati University	
27	COVID-19 Pandemic: Justice Demands for Increasing Deterrence in India	364 - 370

- Jayanta Boruah, Research Scholar, North-Eastern Hill University, Former Assistant Professor of Law & Advocate & Sarthak Aryan, BALLB (3rd Year) National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam

SECTION C: LEGAL ESSAYS

- 28 **Traditional Ecological Knowledge and Biological Diversity Act, 2002: A Critical Analysis** 371 - 378
- Dr. Ravi Kanta Mishra, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, North-Eastern Hill University
- 29 **Trial by Media: A Hindrance in the Path of Justice and Fairness** 379 - 384
- Bidisha Barman, Advocate, Gauhati High Court & Kaustabh Moni Sarma, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 30 **Payment of Rent in Commercial Lease Contracts in Context of the COVID Crisis** 385 -391
- Clarissa D'Lima, Student Kirit P. Mehta School of Law, NMIMS Deemed-to-be University, Mumbai
- 31 **Adultery was Never a Crime: It is a Moral Wrong** 392 - 397
- Aadarsh Kumar Shrivastava, B.A.LL.B. 10th semester, Government New Law College Indore MP
- 32 **The Legal Protection for Consumers in Conducting E-Commerce Activities in India** 398 - 403
- Dikshita Nanda, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 33 **"Rarest of Rare Case"- Capital Punishment** 404 - 408
- Devika Warriar, Bharata Mata School of Legal Studies, Kerala
- 34 **Mob Lynching in India: A Threat to Mankind** 409 -413
- Nabanita Baruah, Student (BALLB 7th Sem), Department of Law, NERIM Law College
- 35 **Biomedical Waste Management during COVID-19 Pandemic in India** 414 - 418
- Farzin Naz, Advocate, Gauhati High Court
- 36 **Impact of Lockdown on Migrant Workers whether a Humanitarian or Human Rights Crisis?** 419 - 426
- Nikhil Moitra, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam
- 37 **Right to Privacy and Data Protection Law in India with a Brief Comparative Analysis with UK and USA** 427 - 433
- Bandana Saikia, Student, Symbiosis Law School Pune
- 38 **Rise of Pedophiles amidst Coronavirus Outbreak** 434 - 440
- Bulbul Kumari, Student, Dharmashastra National Law University, Jabalpur
- 39 **Arrest of Tax Evaders under the Central Goods and Service Tax Act 2017** 441 - 446
- Hunseng Tungkhang, Student, NERIM Law College

SECTION D: CASE COMMENTARY

- 40 **M/S. Nandhini Deluxe v. M/S. Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers Federation Ltd** 447 - 454
- Natesh Kumar, B.COM; LL.B.(HONS.), School of Law, SASTRA Deemed University
- 41 **The Interpretation of the Law of Limitation by the Indian Supreme Court during the COVID-19 Pandemic** 455 - 457
- Dr. Smarita Mohanty, Member, State Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission, Odisha
- 42 **Vineeta Sharma v. Rakesh Sharma** 458 - 460

	- <i>Namrata Chakrabarty, Advocate, Gauhati High Court</i>	
43	Dunlop Pneumatic Tyre Co. Ltd. V. Selfridge & Co. Ltd.	461 - 463
	- <i>Chetna Priyam, BA LLB (Hons.), ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	
44	Anuradha Bhasin v. Union of India	464 - 467
	- <i>Sristi Ray, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Kanika Chugh, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
45	Ashok Kumar Kalra v. Surendra Agnihotori (SLP No. 23599 of 2018)	468 - 470
	- <i>Monalisa Choudhury, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
46	Committee of Creditors Essar Steel India Limited Through Authorized Signatory v. Satish Kumar Gupta and Ors.	471 - 475
	- <i>Rajat Gupta, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam & Vaishnavi Pandey, Student, National Law University and Judicial Academy Assam</i>	
SECTION E: LEGISLATIVE ANALYSIS		
47	Relevance of Narcotics Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPs) Act, 1985	476 - 480
	- <i>Shivangi Pandey, LL.B.(CONST. LAW SPZ.) (5th Year), University of Petroleum & Energy Studies, Dehradun</i>	
48	Analysis of the Assisted Reproductive Technology (Regulation) Bill, 2020	481 - 485
	- <i>Masia Baruah, Student BALLB 6th Semester, NERIM Law College</i>	
SECTION F: BOOK REVIEW		
49	Just Mercy: A Story of Justice and Redemption	486 - 487
	- <i>Aniket Jadhav, Student, Government Law College, Mumbai</i>	
50	Book Review on Judiciary, Judges and Administration of Justice	488 - 489
	- <i>Ishan Mishra, Student, ICFAI University, Dehradun</i>	

SECTION (D) CASE COMMENTARY

COMMITTEE OF CREDITORS OF ESSAR STEEL INDIA LIMITED THROUGH
AUTHORIZED SIGNATORY V. SATISH KUMAR GUPTA AND ORS.

Section:	D
Category:	Case Commentary
Paper Code:	CC-RG-08
Page Number:	471 - 475
Date of Publication:	February 10, 2021
Citation:	Rajat Gupta & Vaishnavi Pandey, Committee of Creditors Essar Steel India Limited Through Authorized Signatory v. Satish Kumar Gupta and Ors., 1, AIJACLA, 471, 471-475, (2021).

DETAILS OF AUTHOR(S)

Rajat Gupta

Student

National Law University and Judicial Academy

Assam

Email id: rajat1998@nluassam.ac.in

Vaishnavi Pandey

Student

National Law University and Judicial Academy

Assam

Email id: vaishnavi@nluassam.ac.in

INTRODUCTION

The Insolvency and Bankruptcy law was introduced to consolidate and amend the laws that would give certainty of process, time, and outcome to creditors, borrowers, and other market participants. It has improved the jurisprudence of insolvency in the country. The case also demonstrates the parliamentary form of government as the Corporate

Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) provisions were clarified even though, the decision of the National Company Law Appellate Tribunal(NCLAT) was pending before the Supreme Court.

This case comment attempts to analyze the judgment of the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India (hereinafter referred to as Supreme Court) in the case of Committee of Creditors of Essar Steel India Limited

through Authorized Signatory v. Satish Kumar Gupta and Ors, which dealt with a pertinent and extremely contentious issue of the Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) under Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (IBC), 2016, and the scope of powers of the Committee of Creditors (CoC) of corporate debtors thereof.

BACKGROUND

The facts of the present case involved a challenge to the decision of the National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT) in the Supreme Court by the Committee of Creditors (CoC), to recover more than the operational creditor.

The Ahmedabad bench of the National Company Law Tribunal (NCLT) approved ArcelorMittal's bid for Essar Steel and their resolution plan was approved by the Committee of Creditors CoC. This was opposed by the operational creditor because they were getting notional payment.¹

In July, the appellate tribunal had ordered for an equal distribution of funds to all creditors and that they should be treated equally. So, all the operational creditors as well as the employees of the company, who have claims below INR 1 crore, should be given

¹ Prachi Bharadwaj, NCLATs order set aside in Essar Steel Insolvency Case; Key issues on Corporate Insolvency Resolution answered, SCC (Dec 20, 2020, 02:12 AM), NCLAT's order set aside in Essar Steel Insolvency case; Key issues on Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process answered | SCC Blog (sconline.com).

all the dues. And, creditors who have claims of more than INR 1 crore, were to recover 60.7% of the dues. A petition was filed by the financial creditors against the National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT's) ruling in the Supreme Court saying the secured creditors have the first rights over the funds and it was also argued that the ruling of the National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT) has exceeded the scope of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code.

SUPREME COURT JUDGEMENT: AN ANALYSIS

The Supreme Court of India on November 15, 2019, through a three-judge constitution bench, delivered a landmark judgment, concerning the supremacy of the creditors over each other.

1. Though under Section 30(2) of the Code the National Company Law Tribunal (NCLT) has powers to examine the decision of the Committee of Creditors (CoC), the Supreme Court held that the commercial decision of the Committee of Creditors (CoC) is paramount. The jurisdiction of the National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT) is also expressly limited. Thus, it is clear that the limited power available, neither National Company Law Tribunal (NCLT) nor National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT) can direct the admission of several claims. *“The decision of what and how much to*

pay each class of creditors is retained with the Committee of Creditors (CoC) also, it should ensure the presence of the corporate debtor during the Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) process. There should be a balance of interests of all the stakeholders and the value of assets should be maximized.”²

2. Further, the Supreme Court clarified the amended Regulation 38 of the Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) Regulations, that fair and equitable treatment of operational creditors does not mean the debts are distributed pro-rata. Treating unequal equally would violate the purpose of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (IBC). The Supreme Court also observed that the National Company Law Tribunal (NCLT) does not have any residual jurisdiction to reject a plan on the ground of inequality.

3. Under section 30(4), the Committee of Creditors (CoC) has the power to approve a resolution plan and the Sub-committees have only administrative work, but their activity needs to be ratified by the Committee of Creditors (CoC). The resolution plan once approved by the Committee of Creditors (CoC) is binding on all stakeholders.

4. Furthermore, the decision of the Appellate Authority was set aside and it was upheld that the

distribution of profits made during the Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) will not go towards the payment of debts of any creditor.³

5. The Supreme Court made it clear that the 330-day limit is not sacrosanct as mark the violation of Article 14, 19 of the Constitution, which means that the creditors will not be pressurized to accept the below-par deal.

ASSETS OF THE INDIAN BANKING SYSTEM ON THE ECONOMY

The problem of Non-Performing Assets (NPA) in the Indian Banking System is one of the most formidable problems in the arena of the Indian Banking System that has a huge impact on the economy. Higher NPA's causes poor recycling of funds which in turn has a deleterious effect on the deployment of credit which further trembles the confidence of investors, depositors, and lenders.

Further, puts pressure on the recycling of funds and reduces the ability of banks to lend more and thus results in lesser interest income. Due to High Non Performing Assets (NPA's) banks may tend to levy higher on advances to sustain Net Interest Margin on one hand and likely to lower the interests on deposits. Banks are required to maintain adequate capital on risk-weighted assets on an ongoing basis which shore

² Ibid.

³ Pallavi Saluja, Essar Steel Judgement: Key Highlights, BAR & BENCH (Dec 13, 2020, 02:10 AM), Essar Steel Judgment: Key Highlights - Bar & Bench (barandbench.com).

up their capital base. Capital has a price tag ranging from 12% to 18% since it's a scarce resource.

The high Non Performing Assets (NPA) has a cascading effect on all important financial ratios of banks Net Interest Margin (NIM), return on assets, profitability, credit contraction which may likely erode the value of stakeholders like shareholders, depositors, lenders, borrowers, employees, and the public at large. With souring NPA's public confidence almost gets ruptured and starts losing confidence in the soundness of the Banking System. An increase in the rate of NPA not only affects banks by posing liquidity issues but also has a huge impact on the economy as a whole.

The Supreme Court order and government move on financial service providers could prove as a huge relief to banks battling high NPA's. Banks are likely to recover almost 90% percent of their amount which are exposed to the Essar Steel account which is 30 % percent more than what they would have garnered out of the National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT) decision, this will improve their profitability and have an articulated impact on the economy and because of capital infusion more money supply will take place in the economy.⁴

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

⁴ Pro. D.S. Rathore, Dr. Sangeeta Malpani, et al., Non Performing Assets of Indian Banking System and its Impact on Economy, 7(6), IOSR-JEF, 21, 21-26, {2016}.

The Apex court's decision not only enables the sale of Essar Steel but opens a way for the banks to recover the dues from the company that is estimated at around INR 40,000 crore which is more than 90% of their dues. It is estimated that the Operational creditors should receive near about INR 1,200 crore. This decision will help them to help improve the financial position of weak public sector banks and increase profitability, as almost all the dues owed by Essar Steel were fully written off by the majority of lenders. The landmark judgment of the Apex Court put to rest on the key questions concerning the treatment of operational and financial creditors, the role of the Committee of Creditors (CoC), National Company Law Tribunal (NCLT), and National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT) in the Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) of a corporate debtor under the Code.

The Apex Court has flawlessly observed the difference between secured and unsecured creditors which is essential for the banking industry. Additionally, by reinstating the Committee of Creditors (CoC) to be the primary decision-maker, the Supreme Court gives commercial wisdom to the lenders. With this landmark judgment, a large number of pending appeals on similar questions of law before the National Company Law Appellate Tribunal (NCLAT) and National Company Law Tribunal (NCLT) were disposed of very soon. Recent news articles and reports have indicated the

framework of distribution of proceeds to financial creditors and operational creditors under the Code on account of protracted litigation (in multiple cases) based on challenges from operational creditors will be revised by the government soon. Such litigation led to delays in the completion of the process and distribution of proceeds to creditors. However, the position of the government regarding this decision as to the settled law for this purpose will clear with time. The Apex court decision will help to improve the financial position of weak public sector banks.

This Judgment should put to rest the question regarding the treatment of creditors and the role of the Committee of Creditors (CoC) in the Corporate Insolvency Resolution Process (CIRP) of a Corporate Debtor under the code. Further, it has articulated the difference between Secured and Unsecured Creditors. It remains interesting to see whether the government will treat this decision as finally settled as a lot of pending cases can dispose of which have a similar cause of concern in the matter.